

A Systematic Review of the Effect of Active Commuting to School on Children's Well-being: A Physical, Psychological, Social, and Academic Approach

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This review aims to gather updated evidence about the effect of active commuting on the well-being of children. The review was conducted following the PRISMA statement. This review included ten studies from a total of 1,187 found through an electronic search. The results indicate that relatively few studies

analyze the correlation between active commuting and children's well-being from a holistic perspective. This review highlights the relationship between active commuting to school and the overall well-being of children.

Well-being is a growing area of research, and its definition varies from discipline to discipline (Dodge et al., 2012). Moreover, it has been studied across various age groups, cultures, communities, and countries, resulting in an assortment of definitions (Pollard & Lee, 2003). Indeed, this debate has made well-being a field of research in its own right (Amerijckx & Humblet, 2013).

Well-being has been defined as “a multidimensional construct incorporating mental/psychological, physical and social dimensions” (Columbo, 1986, p. 288). It is precisely this holistic and integrative framework that we will adopt in this work since we understand that the psychological, physical, and social dimensions are strongly interrelated and must all be taken into account if we wish to obtain a deeper understanding of well-being. Moreover, in this case, when researching childhood, a fourth dimension should be added—the academic dimension—as in previous research (Berasategi et al., 2020; 2021a; 2021b).

Although it is evident that well-being depends on many parallel constructs, there is ample evidence in the literature that social and emotional growth and development in the early years affects well-being from childhood throughout life (Denham, 2006; Mental Health Taskforce, 2004). Furthermore, the experiences to which children are exposed can influence their well-being and future life course, which, over time, may be more difficult to change (Farrar et al., 2007).

Among these experiences, children’s active commuting to school has attracted interest from the educational and scientific community in recent decades (Fagerholm & Broberg, 2011; Shaw et al., 2013). However, several studies have pointed out that active commuting has dramatically decreased in the last two decades, with walking and cycling gradually being replaced by car trips (Fyhri et al., 2011). The reduction of such active mobility has significant negative consequences for children’s well-being, becoming a global concern (Ayllón et al., 2019). Therefore, to address this challenge, active mobility has been proposed as a key alternative because it promotes children’s personal development and well-being from various dimensions (Davison et al., 2008; Riazi et al., 2019).

From a psychological perspective, children's happiness regarding active commuting has been highlighted (Chillon et al., 2016; Morris & Guerra, 2015). Moreover, some studies point out the relationship between active commuting and lower stress and distress (Chillon et al., 2016; Herman & Larouche, 2021). From a physical perspective, several studies have found that children who go to school alone have healthier lifestyle habits (Flint et al., 2014; Yin et al., 2020), increased levels of physical activity (Donaire-Gonzalez et al., 2015), and a reduced risk of cardiovascular disease (De Hartog, 2010). Likewise, it is known that regular physical activity also has positive consequences for the psychological dimension of well-being (Harner et al., 2009) while also increasing self-efficacy (Huang et al., 2018). Moreover, when analyzed from social and academic dimensions, active commuting—defined as walking, cycling, or any other active way of commuting—may also improve social relationships (Jones & Ogilvie, 2012) and children's psychosocial development (Barblett & Maloney, 2010; Shaw et al., 2013).

Specifically, this paper aims to review the existing literature on the impact of the active commute to school on children's well-being. It is expected that active commuting to school will have a positive impact on well-being, affecting its physical (e.g., sense of health), psychological (e.g., level of personal satisfaction or happiness), social (e.g., level and quality of personal relationships, belonging to the community) and academic dimensions (e.g., academic performance). Commuting to school is understood as journeys made from home to school and back. It is not known the extent to which school travel specifically impacts on children's well-being, and knowing the potential benefits can help to implement or strengthen school pathway projects.

A previous review (Waygood et al., 2019) studies similar variables, but focuses more on travel to school as a general variable, and not specifically on active school travel. Therefore, there is a need for a review that looks specifically at the influence of physical activity on the school journey during children's well-being.

Methods

This systematic review was designed and conducted following the Cochrane Collaboration Manual for Systematic Reviews (version 5.0.1; Higgins & Green, 2011). In addition, this manuscript has been drawn up using PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines (Liberati et al., 2009). A protocol was developed and registered on Prospero's website under registration number CRD42021279959.

Criteria for Considering Studies in this Review

Types of studies. Any observational, longitudinal, or transversal studies were considered for inclusion. No experimental and systematic review studies were included in this review. Only primary and original studies were considered.

Types of participants. To be included in the review, articles must report the findings of an original study on children between five and 15 years old.

Types of exposure. This review included studies that must report the effects of active commuting to/from school on the well-being of children. Active commuting is that which is carried out without the use of motorized means of transport.

Types of outcomes. Studies must assess at least one of the following outcomes concerning well-being: (1) life satisfaction level, (2) happiness level, (3) perceived health, (4) level and quality of personal relationships, (5) academic outcomes, and (6) community belonging.

Literature Search

The following databases were electronically searched between March 15 and 17, 2021: MEDLINE (OVID), PsycINFO (EBSCO), Sportdiscus (EBSCO), ERIC (ProQuest), WOS, Teacher Reference

Center (EBSCO), and Education Database (ProQuest). The following terms were included in the search strategy: “children,” “commuting to school,” and “well-being,” or other synonyms of this words. These concepts, synonyms, and pertinent indexed terms were combined using Booleans, truncations, and other operators. All the searches were conducted and adapted to the features of each database (ALR). No limitation was performed in the searches.

To complete the electronic search and ensure the inclusion of all existing literature, reference tracking and other search methods were used in line with the recommendations of Greenhalgh and Peacock (2005).

Study Selection

All documents indexed in two or more databases (duplicates) and those that were non-informative or incorrect were removed by a reviewer (ALR) during the first screening. Only the documents that provided sufficient information to be screened were included in the selection process.

In a second screening process, two authors (ILF and NIM) independently reviewed the title and abstract of all documents to identify those that were potentially relevant. Finally, in the third screening, the reviewers used the full text to independently determine which documents met the inclusion criteria, and these were considered in the systematic review. Any disagreement was resolved by consensus, followed, if required, by scrutiny from a third review author (ALR).

Assessment of Study Quality

To assess the quality of the included studies, the Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies was used (National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute, 2014). Research question,

study population, participant rate, inclusion and exclusion criteria, sample size, prior exposure interest measure, timeframe, exposure-outcome relation, exposure assessment, blinded assessors, follow-up and potential confounding variables were assessed. Two authors (ILF and NIM) independently assessed the quality of each of the studies. Any disagreements were discussed until they reached consensus, and whenever this was not possible, a third author (ALR) was consulted and a final decision was made.

Data Management and Analysis

Two reviewers (ILF and NIM) extracted the main characteristics and data of the included studies in an *ad hoc* designed template. The characteristics extracted were study author, year, country, participant characteristics, comparison, the aim of the study, study design/instrument, exposure (independent variable), outcome (dependent variable), and main results of the study. The authors discussed disagreements until a consensus was reached and when this was not possible, a third author was consulted (ALR). A descriptive analysis of the extracted data was performed in this review.

To assess the agreement between reviewers in the screening phases and quality evaluation, before a consensus between reviewers was reached, observed agreement and Cohen's Kappa (Cerdeira & Villarroel, 2008) were calculated using SPSS[®] statistical software package (version 23.0.0.1, IBM[®] Company.)

Results

Study Selection

A total of 1,187 studies were found in the electronic search, of which 18 were not original and 307 were duplicates. Eight hundred sixty-two

studies were included in the second screening, of which 833 were removed (see Figure 1). The observed agreement between reviewers was 89% (Cohen's kappa = 0.79). Thirty studies were included in the third screening using their full text, but most did not directly study the relationship between the active school commuting and its influence on children's well-being. Finally, ten studies met the criteria for this systematic review and were selected. The observed agreement in this phase was 90% (Cohen's Kappa = 0.7).

Study Quality

Table 1 shows the assessment of the methodological quality of the included studies. The observed agreement between reviewers was 83% and Cohen's Kappa was 0.67. Generally speaking, the quality of the included studies was good. All studies adequately defined their objective, children's characteristics, inclusion and exclusion criteria, the measured exposure, the independent variables, and the dependent variables.

However, none of the studies included sample size justification, blinded outcome assessors, or timeframe information. Moreover, only three studies (Leung & Loo, 2017; García-Hermoso et al., 2017, Hulley et al., 2008) had 50% eligible participation and only two (Stark et al., 2018; Hulley et al., 2008) assessed the exposure more than once.

Characteristics of the Studies

Countries

Six out of the ten studies included in this review were conducted in Europe (including Spain, Austria, Sweden, and England), one in Chile, another in Hong Kong, another in Canada, and the last was international (see Table 2).

Table 1
Quality of Included Studies

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Yes/total (Yes%)
Well-being research													
Chillon et al. (2017)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Nr*	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	6/12 (50%)
García-Hermoso et al. (2017)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	8/12 (66,7%)
Leung & Loo (2017)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	8/12 (66,7%)
Ruiz-Ariza et al. (2015)	Yes	Yes	Nr	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	6/12 (50%)
Stark et al. (2019)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	6/12 (50%)
Westman et al. (2017)	Yes	Yes	Nr	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	6/12 (50%)
Kleszczewska et al. (2020)	Yes	Yes	Nr	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	6/12 (50%)
Ramanathan et al. (2014)	Yes	Yes	Nr	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	6/12 (50%)
Stark et al. (2018)	Yes	Yes	Nr	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	7/12 (58,3%)
Hulley et al. (2008)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Nr	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	8/12 (66,7%)
Yes/total (Yes%)	100%	100%	30%	100%	0%	100%	0%	20%	100%	20%	100%	0%	0%

Q1 = Clear objective; Q2 = Clearly defined population; Q3 = %50 eligible participation; Q4 = Inclusion & exclusion criteria of participants; Q5 = Sample size justification; Q6 = Exposure measured; Q7 = Sufficient timeframe; Q8 = Different level of exposure examined; Q9 = Clear independent variables; Q10 = Exposure assessed more than once; Q11 = Clear dependent variables; Q12 = Outcome assessors blinded.

* Nr, not reported.

Table 2
Characteristics of Included Studies

ID	Study	Country	Exposure Participants	Comparison Participants	Aim of the Study	Design/ Instrument	Exposure. Independent variable	Outcome. Dependent Variable	Results
1	Chilón, Villén-Contreras, Pulido-Martos & Ruiz, 2016	Spain	366 children (172 girls, 194 boys). 7- 11 yr.	No	To analyze the association between active commuting to school and positive health and stress related-variables in Spanish children.	Questionnaires given to students.	Age, gender, mothers' level of education, and the number of active trips to school.	Satisfaction with life, subjective happiness, dispositional optimism (positive health and stress).	Children who actively go to or return from school have a lower level of stress. This association was not significant for the other variables of positive health, subjective happiness, subjective cognitive well-being, positive affect, and negative affect.
3	García-Hermoso, Saavedra, Olloquequi & Ramírez-Vélez, 2017	Chile	389 adolescents (193 girls, 196 boys). 12-13 yr.	No	To examine the relationship between duration of walking or otherwise actively commuting to school and academic achievement.	Self-reported questionnaire, students' grades, an electronic scale, the Physical Activity Questionnaire for Adolescents, questionnaire given to mothers, a scale based on Graffar's modified method, and a questionnaire given to parents.	Active commuting, non-active commuting, anthropometry, screen time, physical activity, maternal education, socioeconomic status, and neonatal chart.	Academic achievement.	Academic attainment was higher in language and mathematics for adolescents with 30 to 60 min of active commuting to school.

Table 2 (Continued)

ID	Study	Country	Exposure Participants	Comparison Participants	Aim of the Study	Design/ Instrument	Exposure. Independent variable	Outcome. Dependent Variable	Results
7	Leung & Loo (2017)	Hong Kong	393 children (182 girls, 171 boys). 5-12 yr.	No	To study children's travel behavior for journeys to and from school and to understand children's subjective feelings of their happiness experiences.	Questionnaires given to children and parents.	Age, gender, travel mode, active commuting and passive commuting, confidence in self-care ability, and perception of road-crossing safety.	Happiness: subjective feelings of well-being in their travel and daily life.	Children engaging in active transport rated their journeys as happier. Accompanied children also rated their journeys as happier. Children who perceived themselves as more capable of taking care of themselves independently rated their lives as happier.
10	Ruiz-Ariza, de la Torre-Cruz, Fedecillas-Peiró & Martínez-López, 2015	Spain	1012 adolescents (582 girls, 430 boys). Mean age 14.42 yr.	No	To analyze the association between active displacement and psychological health indicators.	Questionnaires given to adolescents.	Age, BMI, gender, active commuting (min/day), and mother's educational attainment.	Subjective happiness, psychological well-being, psychological distress, and body image.	Adolescents who spent more than 15 minutes a day in active commuting had higher happiness and well-being and lower distress.
12	Stark, Singleton, Uhlmann, 2019	Austria	129 children (57 girls, 72 boys). Mean age 9.9 yr.	No	To examine relations between children's mode use on school trips, attitudes, and PWB.	Self-administered questionnaire for children.	Age, sex, travel mode used on school trips, and travel-related attitudes.	Well being and attitudes concerning the given travel modes.	The tests did not reveal any significant correlation between active commuting and well-being.

Table 2 (Continued)

ID	Study	Country	Exposure Participants	Comparison Participants	Aim of the Study	Design/ Instrument	Exposure. Independent variable	Outcome. Dependent Variable	Results
15	Westman, Olsson, Gärling & Friman, 2017	Sweden	344 children (165 girls, 179 boys). 10-15 yr.	No	To investigate whether travel mode, travel time, and activities during travel influence children's satisfaction with their travel to school, their current mood, and their cognitive performance after arriving at school.	The questionnaire and adapted version of the Satisfaction with Travel Scale and a word-fluency test for children.	Gender, grade, travel time and mode, and activities during travel	Children's satisfaction with their travel to school, current mood, and cognitive performance after arriving at school.	Traveling by school bus and walking or cycling was perceived to be of a higher quality. Children who engaged in conversation during their journeys reported higher quality and more positive feelings. A shorter journey was perceived to be of a higher quality and resulting in more positive feelings. Children traveling for longer durations performed better in the word-fluency test.

Table 2 (Continued)

ID	Study	Country	Exposure Participants	Comparison Participants	Aim of the Study	Design/ Instrument	Exposure. Independent variable	Outcome. Dependent Variable	Results
16	Kleszczewska, Mazur, Bucksch, Dzielska, Brindley, Michalska, 2020.	Inter-national	56834 children, (28815 girls, 28019 boys). Mean age 13.43 yr.	No	To investigate the relationship between modes of transport to school and subjective complaints among schoolchildren.	Self-reported checklist.	Active transport to school.	Psychosomatic complaints (headache, abdominal pain, back pain, and dizziness; depression, nervousness, irritability, bad mood, difficulty sleeping).	Cycling showed a protective effect against psychosomatic complaints in some countries, and walking showed a protective association for children and adolescents in only one country. It is a greater protective effect of active transport to school concerning psychological rather than somatic complaints.

Table 2 (Continued)

ID	Study	Country	Exposure Participants	Comparison Participants	Aim of the Study	Design/ Instrument	Exposure. Independent variable	Outcome. Dependent Variable	Results
24	Ramanathan, O'Brien, Faulkner & Stone, 2014	Canada	5423 children (equal proportions of girls and boys). Mean age 8.7 yr.	No	To analyze associations between active commuting to school and sustainable happiness and well-being indicators among Canadian children and their parents at the "School Travel Planning" expansion schools.	Questionnaires to families.	Age, sex, school travel measures and emotions.	Parent perceived benefits of travel mode on dimensions of well-being (Physical, emotional, community, and environmental).	Parents and children who used active school travel reported more positive emotions. Parents of active travelers reported stronger connections to dimensions of well-being. Active school travel had the strongest association with parents' perceptions of their child's well-being, and positive emotions.

Table 2 (Continued)

ID	Study	Country	Exposure Participants	Comparison Participants	Aim of the Study	Design/ Instrument	Exposure. Independent variable	Outcome. Dependent Variable	Results
26	Stark, Meschik, Singleton & Schützhöfer, 2018	Austria	152 children (78 girls, 74 boys). Mean age 9.6 yr.	No	To investigate the relationship between mode use on school trips and the psychological well-being of children.	Questionnaire to children and parents.	Mode use on school travel	Psychological well-being: how do they feel during the first school lesson and the last lesson.	Active school travel is positively associated with children's psychological well-being. Parents reported strong positive associations between active commuting modes and the well-being of their children.
30	Hulley, Bentley, Clough, Fishlock, Morrell, O'Brien & Radmore, 2008	England	99 children (53 girls, 46 boys). Mean age 7 yr.	No	To test the hypothesis that children who walk further to school experience increased arousal and affective valence.	The children's feeling scale and the children's felt arousal scale, Pedometer.	Age, the distance between home and school, and the travel mode.	Children feeling scale, children felt arousal, and affective states.	There was evidence that the children who walked further reported a greater increase in their children's felt arousal scale.

Aim of the Studies

The studies generally aimed to analyze the association between active commuting to school and positive health, emotional, academic, or social variables (Table 2). Specifically, most of the studies were concerned with psychological variables such as psychological well-being (Ruiz-Ariza et al., 2015; Ramanathan et al., 2014; Stark et al., 2018; Stark 2019), happiness (Leung & Loo, 2017; Ramanathan et al., 2014), stress (Chillon et al., 2016), affective valance (Hulley et al., 2008) or children's mood (Westman et al., 2017). In addition, there were also two studies related to academic achievement (García-Hermoso et al., 2017; Westman et al., 2017) and another with a more behavioral approach (Kleszewska et al., 2020). However, none of the papers reviewed examined all the dimensions mentioned in our review.

Study Design and Instrument

All the articles included in this review were cross-sectional studies that used questionnaires as an instrument, and most of them were self-administered questionnaires for children. For example, García-Hermoso and colleagues (2017), Leung and Loo (2017), Ramanathan and colleagues (2014), and Stark and colleagues (2018) included both questionnaires for parents and children (Table 2).

Results of the Studies

All but one study (Stark et al., 2019) found a positive and significant association between active commuting to school and children's well-being. Most of the studies highlighted the benefits for well-being from an emotional or psychological perspective. In particular, Chillon and colleagues (2016) found a lower level of stress, although they did not find significant associations with other variables of positive health, subjective happiness, subjective cognitive well-being, positive affect,

and negative affect. On the other hand, Leung and Loo (2017) found higher happiness levels in active commuting children. Moreover, children who perceived themselves as more capable of taking care of themselves rated their lives as happier. In the same vein, Ruíz-Ariza and colleagues (2015) found a significant correlation between active commuting and greater happiness and well-being and lower stress levels. Finally, Westman and colleagues (2017) pointed out that traveling by school bus and walking or cycling were perceived to be higher quality experiences than traveling by car. Moreover, children who engaged in conversation during their journeys reported higher quality and more positive feelings than those who engaged in solitary activities. In addition, a shorter journey was perceived as having a higher quality and resulting in more positive feelings. Finally, this study also concluded that children who actively commute for more than 15 minutes performed better in the word-fluency test if using their smartphones or doing a combination of activities during their journeys.

In the studies of Ramanathan and colleagues (2003) and Stark and colleagues (2018), parents and children who used active school travel reported more positive emotions than passive travelers, and active school travel had the strongest association with parents' perceptions of their child's well-being. Furthermore, positive emotions (parent and child) on the school trip were also significantly related to well-being. Finally, Hulley and colleagues (2008) found that active commuters scored higher on the children's felt arousal scale.

However, the only international study (and with the largest sample size; Kleszczewska et al., 2020), found that although cycling showed a protective effect against psychosomatic complaints in some countries, walking was a protective factor for children and adolescents in only one country. Moreover, this study also found that active commuting to school had a greater protective effect for psychological than somatic complaints.

García-Hermoso and colleagues (2017), from a more academic perspective, found that academic attainment in language and mathematics was higher in adolescents that actively commute to school than

in non-commuters. Moreover, students who had 30–60 minutes of active commuting to school were more likely to obtain high academic achievement in language and mathematics. Finally, Stark and colleagues (2019) found no significant correlations in relation to academic achievement, although they found a tendency toward an association between active commuting and well-being.

Discussion

This paper aims to review the existing literature on the impact of the active commute to school on children's well-being. We identified ten studies that assessed the influence of going to school actively on the well-being of children aged five to 15 years old. Nine research studies reported a positive correlation between active commuting and aspects associated with children's well-being.

If we follow the holistic perspective on which the conceptualization of this work has been based (Columbo, 1986; Berasategi et al., 2020), the first factor to highlight is that the psychological dimension is the one that has been mostly analyzed. Nine of the ten studies include at least one psychological variable, specifically happiness (Leung & Loo, 2017; Ramanathan et al., 2013), stress (Chillon et al., 2016), affective valance (Hulley et al., 2008), or children's mood (Westman et al., 2017). In addition, four articles focus specifically on well-being, although they only consider its psychological dimension (Ruiz-Ariza et al., 2015; Ramanathan et al., 2013; Stark et al., 2018; Stark 2019).

Within this psychological dimension, two of the articles (Leung & Loo, 2017; Ruíz-Ariza et al., 2015) claim that children who actively commute to school have a higher level of happiness. This can be related to the body of research suggesting that regular physical activity leads to higher levels of happiness in both children and adults (Khazae-Pool et al., 2015; Tse et al., 2014; Yook et al., 2017).

In a similar vein, the study by Chillon and colleagues (2016) also indicates that children who walk or cycle to school have lower levels

of stress and distress. In the literature, we can find numerous articles reporting significant relationships between physical activity and stress reduction (Nguyen-Michel, 2006; Penedo & Dahn, 2005; Schultchen et al., 2019). With a very similar perspective, Westman and colleagues (2017) also report that children who must make a short trip to school experience more positive feelings. Indeed, there is an extensive literature showing significant relationships between distance to school and its consequences for choice of travel mode, physical and psychological health or travel risks, and other factors (Lee et al., 2013; Mei et al., 2019; Panter et al., 2011; Van Goeverden & De Boer, 2013). In this regard, it is also interesting to note the numerous studies claiming that students who live closer to school are more likely to choose an active commuting mode (Chica-Olmo et al., 2018; Yeung et al., 2008).

From a more social perspective, Westman and colleagues (2017) also pointed out that one of the relevant factors for increasing the positive feelings mentioned above may be the personal relationships or conversations established during the journey to school. The literature also suggests that children with better social relationships feel happier and have more positive feelings (Holder & Coleman, 2009; McGregor et al., 2006; Tkach and Lyubomirsky, 2006). Therefore, it stands to reason that the findings of Ramanathan and colleagues (2003) and Westman and colleagues (2017) assume that going to school actively with schoolmates leads to better relationships with peers.

From a more physical perspective, in an international study, Kleszczewska and colleagues (2020) found that commuting to school by bicycle showed a higher protective effect against psychosomatic problems. In this regard, the existing literature claims that cycling to school (or to work in the case of adults) increases the duration of physical activity (Donaire-Gonzalez et al., 2015), prevents cardiovascular disease (De Hartog, 2010), and increases self-efficacy (Huang et al., 2018). In addition, more extensive relationships have been found with

other variables such as disease risk or obesity, since those with a higher level of physical activity have better physical health (Kokkinos, 2012; Rodhes et al., 2017).

Finally, the two studies related to academic achievement (García-Hermoso et al., 2017; Westman et al., 2017) found that active commuting to school improves performance in language and mathematics. In this regard, several studies have pointed out that curriculum-based physical activity in school may improve the academic achievement and psychological health of children (Bunketorp et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2012; Trudeau & Shephard, 2008), although Phansikar and colleagues (2019) argue that future studies should conduct longitudinal studies and use objective measures to evaluate the correlation between these variables.

Conclusions

In this review, most of the articles highlight the link between active commuting to school and the well-being of schoolchildren. However, it is also necessary to delve deeper into this topic to gather more conclusive results since of the ten articles analyzed here, no relationship was found between the variables under study. In this sense, it will be necessary to analyze the well-being dimension from a holistic point of view where the social, academic, physical, and psychological dimensions are considered.

Finally, it would also be interesting to determine how children's autonomous travel has an impact on these outcomes—that is, the extent to which the improvement in well-being factors is related to active commuting and autonomous travel since the studies analyzed how the active, but not the autonomous, dimension influences these outcomes. Thus, future research must measure these two dimensions and analyze separately their influence on children's well-being.

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